

SOCIAL INNOVATION FOR REVITALIZING FOREST-DEPENDENT COMMUNITIES

Professor Maria Nijnik and Dr Simo Sarkki discuss social innovations and their importance in revitalising forest-dependent communities

Forests provide a long list of benefits to people. Sustainable use of forests contributes to the well-being of local communities. It helps them tackle challenges and address the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDG). Sustainability in forest use is enhanced by regulations and improved by market incentives and policy instruments. These instruments, however, may overlook the realities of forest-dependent communities. The promotion of *social innovation* can assist in addressing sustainability by complementing other policy instruments.

What is social innovation?

Aiming at improving human well-being, social innovation can create new responses to pressing social demands. It necessarily relies on the voluntary engagement of civil society actors and is usually described as focusing attention on ideas and solutions that create social values, as well as the processes through which they are generated¹.

H2020 SIMRA Project

The Social Innovation in Marginalised Rural Areas (SIMRA) project, funded by the EU Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme, Grant Agreement 677622 comprises 26 partner organisations and is co-ordinated by The James Hutton Institute. It advances understanding of social innovation and innovative governance in agriculture, forestry and rural development, and how to boost them, particularly in marginalised rural areas.

SIMRA defines social innovation as “the reconfiguring of social practices, in response to societal challenges, which seeks to enhance outcomes on societal well-being and necessarily includes the engagement of civil society actors”².

Social innovation examples

SIMRA has built an extensive database of social innovation cases from around 325 projects from Europe and North Africa. Selected examples are now available on SIMRA’s digital portal³.

Social innovation examples in forest-dependent communities in Finland and the UK

- A collaborative management group of diverse local stakeholders and representatives of state forestry enterprises who plans and monitors loggings to secure opportunities for nature-based tourism, reindeer herding and recreation in Muonio, Finland.
- A social innovative, community ownership-based management of local woodlands in Lochcarron, Scotland, which responds to social needs by creating opportunities for local employment, housing, skills enhancement and cultural heritage.

What triggers social innovation?

Social innovation usually emerges as a response to triggers, both positive and negative. Policy instruments and management strategies can become negative triggers of forest-related social innovation, for example:

- Industrial loggings may have negative impacts on local and small-scale use of the forest by communities (e.g. for nature-based tourism or non-wood forest products). Local people would

benefit from more sustainable forest management and could respond with social innovations that advance sustainability.

- Financial incentives, provided to landowners to encourage them to exclude their forests from loggings, have shown promise in many locations; however, their continual funding is insecure and the question arises whether a possible erosion of forest-based ways of life can be compensated monetarily. Moreover, within the institutional settings of some countries, the restriction of timber harvesting could encourage illegal loggings, with the emergence of a shadow forest economy.
- A protected area that enhances ecological sustainability may restrict or even exclude local ways of using and relating to the forest. Non-compliance with rules perceived by local communities to be unfair could lead to potential conflicts and undermine the sustainability of the entire social-ecological system.

Social innovation to make a change?

The following table shows how three tiers of forest-related social innovation are linked to the UN SDG⁴:

Reconfigurations in perceptions of sustainability	→	General logic of SDGs: Benefits of development are not equally shared. Sustainable development should be “Leaving no one behind”.
Reconfigurations in rules of forest management and use	→	SDG 16: Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions. “Ensure responsive, inclusive, participatory and representative decision-making at all levels”.
Reconfigurations in operational management of a forest and its multipurpose use	→	SDG 15: Life on Land. Multiple ecological, economic, social and cultural roles of forests to be guaranteed.

Lessons learned from social innovations

Social innovations associated with reconfiguring perceptions of sustainable forest management primarily aim at securing continuance of local ways of life and increasing well-being. Revitalization of forest-dependent communities requires that forest management is economically beneficial for people, providing the material basis for them to continue living in the locality. Sustainability is perceived as a sense of community and identity, good social relationships within and between communities and towards other stakeholders (e.g. forest companies; authorities), and also as local stewardships, which respect people and nature.

Social innovations for reconfiguring rules for the use and management of forests include collaborative management groups for planning loggings, changing ownership of forests, introducing innovative grassroots practices to monitor sustainability in using natural assets, and pilot projects to introduce new participatory practices in forest management.

The SIMRA cases highlight capacities for the revitalisation of continuous cover forestry practices, locally beneficial nature-based tourism, use of non-wood forest products, grazing practices, gaming, etc. These practices do not necessarily require discontinuing commercial forestry or forest protection, but rather that the social innovations for reconfiguring forest management and use are characterised by movements towards sustainable, multifunctional forestry.

From local to global – and back

Social innovations usually emerge at a grassroots level, but may be mainstreamed and up- and out-scaled. Local innovations are often manifestations of global trends. However, without concrete changes on the ground and at various locations, global trends remain hypothetical. Social innovations therefore need to be supported at multiple levels, including as part of global change strategies by policy and governance towards a future that secures environmentally sustainable and socially equitable forest management and use.

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References

¹Nijnik, M., Secco, L., Miller, D., Melnykovych, M. (in press) Can social innovation make a difference in forest-dependent communities? *Forest Policy and Economics*.

²Kluvánková, T., Špaček, M., Brnkalakova, S., Slee, B., Nijnik, M., Valero, D., Miller, D., Bryce, R., Szabo, T., Kozova, M., Gezik, V. (2018). Understanding social innovation for well-being of forest dependent communities: a preliminary theoretical framework. *Forest Policy and Economics*, 97, 163–174.

³www.simra-h2020.eu/

⁴<https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/?menu=1300>